

Biomonitoring And Zonal Cartography Of *Loxodonta Africana Cyclotys* (Proboscidea, Mammalia) Activity In The Era-Congo/Mai-Ndombe Redd⁺ Concession In Democratic Republic Of The Congo

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ABSTRACT

The Democratic Republic of the Congo is a biodiversity hotspot. It is amongst one of the most important fauna reserves either in Africa or in the world. Yet, its fauna is dangerously threatened thru the poaching upsurge and of the smuggling. Worldwide, studies show that a certain number of victim animal species is notching up on the red list of threatened species of IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature), it is the case of African elephants of which the habitat is more and more restricted because of the demographic pressure and human activities. In order to protect this natural ecological inheritance and of its habitat, a scientific assignment was performed some months ago in this forest zone for confirming the existence of these elephants. This prospective study aimed the confirmation of the existence of elephants in this geographical area as a main objective. The specific objectives of this study were the direct and/or indirect observation in order to collect the presence indexes of elephants in this zone on the one hand and on the other hand to elaborate the map indicating the activity zones. Several elephant indexes (fresh and recent droppings, tracks and berries) were observed. The activity zone of elephants is located out of as well as in the concession ERA-CONGO/MAI-NDOMDE REDD⁺. Therefore, the forest block of Ntombe Nzale grouping (mainly Ngeleku, Olingi-oyei and Ilee-Makaba villages) in the Mai-Ndombe province constitutes a priority zone for the biodiversity conservation.

Key words: *Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mai Ndombe Province, Ntombe Nzale, Biodiversity conservation, Loxodonta africana cyclotys*

INTRODUCTION

The monitoring of wildlife or bio-monitoring is a fundamental step necessary to the management and the biodiversity conservation [1-3]. In fact, despite the natural loss of biological resources, it is well known that man has sped the extinction rhythm up drastically. In tropical regions and precisely in the Republic Democratic of the Congo (DRC), the shortage of these resources could be a serious threat for the survival of the forest zone populations. In particular, that's the case of excessive withdrawal of big mammals having relatively a low reproduction rate like elephants. This withdrawal does not allow the animal storage to be reformed, hence the need for protection [4].

The Mai-Ndombe REDD⁺ d'ERA Congo/Wildlife Works (WW) project is located in Maindombe province (formerly Bandundu), at the west of DRC. The project is located on the western bank of Mai-Ndombe lake, and approximately covers 300 000 hectares of forests at high density, marshy forest and the savanna. Mai-Ndombe REDD⁺ lands are part of Ngiri-Tumba-Mai-Ndombe wetlands, the greatest wetland of

global importance in the world known by the Ramsar Convention [5]. In the frame of its program, REDD⁺ has just reinforced the partnership for Congo Basin Forest for this territory is rich in biodiversity of a particular attention. At the South-east of this area is found forests and savanna which are an important refuge of elephants group living under threat from poachers.

In the view of protecting this high value animal for the conservation and totally protected by the Congolese government that a scientific mission was carried out in this forest area in order to confirm the existence of elephants found a few months before. The confirmation of elephant existence in this geographical area was the fundamental objective of this prospective study. On the one hand to proceed to the direct and/or indirect observation in order to collect the elephant presence indexes in the area, and on the other hand to draw up the map pointing out the activity zones of elephants and install infrared-triggered camera traps (camera trapping) in this area, were the specific objectives of this study.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

This study was carried out in the forest block, at a certain time was exploited by FORESCOM firm, in the Ntombe Nzale grouping mainly in Ngeleku, Olingi-oyei and Ilee-Makaba villages (Province of Mai-Ndombe, DRC). This zone is located at a distance of about 60km. And it should be notify that the exploration of these animals was also performed out of the project area precisely in the forest of Panza I & II and Ngolo villages. The vegetation of the inspected area is consists of the following categories: mixed primary forest with sealed undergrowth, marshy forest, colonized forest by Marantaceae, liana forest, secondary forest and savannas.

Methodology

The monitoring of wildlife in situ was performed by a technique called “recce” or “recognition walking” [6]. It is based on direct observation of animals or on the record of their activity traces (footprints, droppings, nests and leftovers). The team worked on the tracks of elephants found in the area. Data collected on the tracks were fresh and recent droppings of elephants which are considered like undeniable indexes of their presence. We also recorded the footprints, leftovers (waste food) as well as their berries. The mission was conducted between 11 and 25 October 2014. As material, we used a Panasonic brand digital camera (3 megapixels, 3X optical zoom) in order to snap pictures and a Garmin brand GPS X12 for recording the geographical coordinates.

RESULTS

Several indexes of elephants (fresh and recent droppings, tracks, footprints and berries) were observed as shown in the following figures.

Figure 1 : *Loxodonta africana cyclotys*

Several indexes of elephants (fresh and recent droppings, tracks, footprints and berries) were observed as shown in figure 2 below.

Figure 2 : Some indexes of elephants (a-e) and the trapping camera (f) fixed in situ

The map of the area pointing out different activity sites of elephants is shown in the figure 3 below.

As shown from the above map, the activity area of elephants is also located both outside and in the concession.

DISCUSSION

The southeast forest of the ERA-CONGO/MAI-NDOMBE REDD+ concession that is located in the Ntombe-Nzale grouping that abounds inside of it a lot of elephants (*Loxodonta africana cyclotys*). It's a high value species for conservation as fully protected by the Congolese government. Besides elephants, it should be noted that other animal species of high

value are present at this area such as buffaloes (*Syncerus affter*), the giant pangolin (*Manis gigantea*) and some non-human primates (*Pan paniscus*) in this forest block.

This forest is still keeping its natural state and is a place of refuge for several animal species fully or partially protected by law n° 82-002 du 28 may 1982 on the regulation of hunting in DRC [4]. This ecosystem is consisted of a primary forest having a very varied vegetation namely the mixed forest with opened undergrowth, the mixed forest with closed undergrowth, the Marantaceae forest, the periodically flooded forest, the *Gilbertiodendron dewervrei* forest, liana forest, the marshy forest and the savannas. The pressure on this forest is very low because of the low population density and especially the subsistence farming.

The local populations are interested only to fishing and hunting around the villages. Thus, as regards conservation, it constitutes a priority area for biodiversity conservation according to the participatory mapping because it is less disrupted by human activities. The forest geostrategic position being at the border with Panza I & II and Ngolo is an essential asset for a development plan under the protection of this high value species for the conservation. The project authorities could negotiate with the local communities so that they can be involved in this process in order to reduce the threats to elephants of this area.

In fact, the presence of these animals inside this forest would bring profit to the population as regards the ecotourism. The implementation of a strategy/policy of management of elephants through the community conservation could for this purpose be a better way to ensure a fair sharing benefit between local communities. This approach would generate jobs for the local population in accordance with the Nagoya protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity [4, 7].

CONCLUSION

A prospecting mission of elephants in the forest of Ngeleku, Olingi-oyei, Ilee-Makaba, Panza I & II and Ngolo villages confirmed the presence of these animals. It is namely about indices such as droppings, footprints, leftovers and berries. Our team also observed some traces of buffalo (*Syncerus cafffer*) and non-human primates like bonobos (*Pan paniscus*). The presence of these animals protected by law n° 82-002 du 28 may 1982 on the regulation of hunting practices in DRC, precisely in this part of the republic, makes of this forest a priority conservation area.

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